

Lab 2

Data Mining Technology for Business and Society

Near Duplicate Detection: Problem Definition

Near Duplicate Detection Problem:

Given in input a set of elements, the NDD problem consists in finding all unordered couples of elements that are near duplicate.

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Naive Method:

Compute the similarity value of all unordered couples of elements. \implies Too Many Couples!!! $n(n-1)/2 = O(n^2)$
 $n :=$ input set size

If n is "small" the Naive Method is ok.

If n is "not small" we need a different method to solve the problem.

Near Duplicate Detection: Problem Definition 4 Docs

Near Duplicate Detection Problem:

Given in input a set of elements (**documents**), the NDD problem consists in finding all unordered couples of elements (**documents**) that are near duplicate.

Duplicate:

Two documents are **duplicate** if they have different identifiers and same content.

Near Duplicate:

Two documents are **near duplicate** if they have different identifiers and similar content.

Near Duplicate Detection: Near Dups vs. Dups

Near Duplicate vs. Duplicate

- Which is the maximum number of near-duplicate that we can have? $n(n-1)/2 = O(n^2)$
- If did_x is a duplicate of did_y , is did_y a duplicate of did_x ? **Yes.**
- If did_x is a near-duplicate of did_y , is did_y a near-duplicate of did_x ? **Yes.**
- Is did_x a duplicate of itself? **No.**
- Is did_x a near-duplicate of itself? **No.**
- If did_x is a duplicate of did_y , and did_y is a duplicate of did_z , is did_x a duplicate of did_z ? **Yes.**
- If did_x is a near-duplicate of did_y , and did_y is a near-duplicate of did_z , is did_x a near-duplicate of did_z ? **No.**

Near Duplicate Detection: Pipeline 4 Docs

We are not solving the NDD problem,
we are reducing the number of pairs of documents to check :)

Only for reducing the
number of pairs to check
to find the
near-duplicate :\

Shingling

Shingling

$\text{Shingling}(w=3, \text{"I love my dog, and I love my cat too."}) = \{(?), (?), (?), \dots\}$

Shingling

$\text{Shingling}(w=3, \text{"I love my dog, and I love my cat too."}) = \{(\text{and}, \text{i}, \text{love}), (\text{my}, \text{cat}, \text{too}), (\text{my}, \text{dog}, \text{and}), (\text{dog}, \text{and}, \text{i}), (\text{i}, \text{love}, \text{my}), (\text{love}, \text{my}, \text{cat}), (\text{love}, \text{my}, \text{dog})\}$

Near Duplicate Detection Pipeline

Only for reducing the number of pairs to check to find the near-duplicates :\
\\

$$\text{Jaccard}(A, B) = |A \cap B| / |A \cup B|$$

Jaccard(A, B) = ???

$S_1 = \text{Shingling}(w=3, \text{"I love my dog, and I love my cat too."}) = \{(?), (?), (?), \dots\}$

$S_2 = \text{Shingling}(w=3, \text{"I love my cat, and I love my dog too."}) = \{(?), (?), (?), \dots\}$

Jaccard(S_1, S_2) = ???

$$\text{Jaccard}(A, B) = |A \cap B| / |A \cup B|$$

$$\text{Jaccard}(A, B) = 5/8$$

$S_1 = \text{Shingling}(w=3, \text{"I love my dog, and I love my cat too."}) = \{(\text{and, i, love}), (\text{my, cat, too}), (\text{my, dog, and}), (\text{dog, and, i}), (\text{i, love, my}), (\text{love, my, cat}), (\text{love, my, dog})\}$

$S_2 = \text{Shingling}(w=3, \text{"I love my cat, and I love my dog too."}) = \{(\text{cat, and, i}), (\text{i, love, my}), (\text{and, i, love}), (\text{my, dog, too}), (\text{love, my, cat}), (\text{my, cat, and}), (\text{love, my, dog})\}$

$$\text{Jaccard}(S_1, S_2) = 2/5$$

AppxJaccard(A, B) by Min-Hashing

$$\text{Jaccard}(A, B) = 5/8$$

$$\text{Min-Hashing}(A) = [2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 2, 1, 1, 0, 2]$$

$$\text{Min-Hashing}(B) = [1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 2, 0, 0, 0, 0]$$

$$\text{AppxJaccard}(A, B) = (0+1+1+1+1+1+0+0+1+0)/10 = 6/10 = 3/5$$

AppxJaccard(A, B) by Min-Hashing: ~~permutations~~

Replace permutations with Universal-Hash-Functions:

$$h(x) = ((a*x+b)\%p)\%n$$

$a > 0$, $b \geq 0$,
 $p > n$ and **PRIME**.
 $n = |U|$

AppxJaccard(A, B) by Min-Hashing: ~~permutations~~

Replace permutations with Universal-Hash-Functions:

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Near Duplicate Detection Pipeline

Only for reducing the number of pairs to check to find the near-duplicates :\
\\

Locality Sensitive Hashing

$$n=r*b$$
$$p= 1-(1-j**r)**b$$
$$n= 32 = 8*4 = r*b$$

$$j=0.95 \implies p=0.987$$
$$j=0.90 \implies p=0.894$$
$$j=0.85 \implies p=0.719$$
$$j=0.80 \implies p=0.520$$

Sets of Min-Hashing Sketches

Only for reducing the
number of pairs to check
to find the
near-duplicates :\
FP?
FN?

Near Duplicate Detection Pipeline

